

A STUDY OF THE COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF DIGLYCYLETHYLENEDIAMINE WITH BIVALENT METALS

BY AMIYA KUMAR CHAKRABURTTY, NRIPENDRA NATH GHOSH AND PRIYADARANJAN RĀY

Diglycylethylenediamine, $(-\text{CH}_2\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_2$, has been found to form complexes with bivalent metals like copper, nickel, zinc, cadmium and magnesium, acting as a quadridentate ligand by furnishing four points of attachment from its four nitrogen atoms.

The determination of the two acid dissociation constants (k^*_1 and k^*_2) of the ligand base and a quantitative study of the mechanism of formation and decomposition of the complexes of diglycylethylenediamine with the five bivalent metal ions, viz. Cu^{++} , Ni^{++} , Zn^{++} , Cd^{++} and Mg^{++} , have been made by the physicochemical method developed by Bjerrum.

The stability of the corresponding complexes were found to follow the order $\text{Cu} > \text{Ni} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cd} > \text{Mg}$, having the pK values 8.13, 5.42, 4.31, 3.33, and 0.54, respectively.

In the case of copper and nickel the stepwise hydrolysis of the complex cations was studied and the two hydrolysis constants K_{h_1} and K_{h_2} determined. The electrolytic dissociation constants, $k^*_{b_1}$ and $k^*_{b_2}$, of the corresponding complex bases were also derived therefrom.

The complex copper and nickel bases and their chlorides have been isolated in a pure state and their properties studied. The colour of the bases and of the salts differ widely suggesting a difference in the nature of the complex cations in the two cases. The complex bases probably belong to the penetration type with planar hybrid dsp^2 bonds, whereas the salts are characterised mostly by ionic or ion-dipole co-ordination bonds. This has been supported by the measurement of magnetic moments of the compounds.

Pfeiffer and Saure (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1941, 157, 116) in a comprehensive study of the mechanism of biuret reaction and of the structure of the resulting compounds have described the preparation and properties of a large number of co-ordination complexes formed by various organic reagents, similar in character to biuret; as for example, glycyamide, glycy-anilide, glycyglycine, diglycylethylenediamine, etc., with metals of the first transitional series (Cu and Ni). Of these, diglycylethylenediamine (I), which is assumed to serve as a quadridentate ligand, was first prepared by them in the form of hygroscopic needles. This was found by them to give a deep violet solution with copper acetate or copper hydroxide and alkali, but the resulting complex could not be isolated in a pure crystalline condition.

In continuation of the work on the study of the complex compounds of biguanide, dicyandiamidine and thiodicyandiamidine (guanylthiourea), which had been carried out in this laboratory for several years, it was considered of interest to investigate the formation, stability and the preparation in pure crystalline state of the complex compounds of diglycylethylenediamine with bivalent metals like copper, nickel, zinc, cadmium, etc. As a result, we have succeeded in preparing the copper and nickel complexes of the ligand, in the form of both as free bases as well as their salts. These have been found to possess a structure (II) as shown below.

(where X=OH or a univalent anion).

This structure, however, differs from that suggested by Pfeiffer and Saure (*loc. cit.*) for complexes with ligands of this type. Taking, for instance, the case of glycyamide, they have discussed about two possible structures of the inner-metallic type (a) and (b) for its copper complex, as represented below:

But they further pointed out that as diglycylorthophenylenediamine, in which the two anido-N atoms are linked by a short bridge, gave a violet-coloured copper compound, preference should be given to the structure (a).

The copper and nickel complexes of diglycylethylenediamine prepared by us are highly soluble in water and show distinctly different colours in alkaline and neutral solutions. They have been isolated both as free base as well as salts, showing that they are not inner-metallic complex of the type described by Pfeiffer and Saure (*loc. cit.*). The complex copper base forms red-violet crystals which give a deep permanganate-red solution in water; while the salt (chloride) of the complex base forms deep blue flakes. The complex nickel base gives rise to a bright yellow hygroscopic powder which forms a deep yellow solution in water. The yellow base is diamagnetic. But the salt (chloride) of the yellow base is bluish green and has been found to be paramagnetic, giving a moment value of $2.8\mu_B$, identical with that for a simple nickel ion. This seems to suggest a difference in the type of the co-ordination bonds in the base and the salt. The diamagnetic base consequently possesses a planar structure with strong dsp^2 hybrid bonds giving rise to a penetration complex, while the salt may be represented as an ionic complex with ion-dipole bonds or as an associated complex with weak sp^2d hybrid bonds, resonating with the ionic type. The same distinction may be assumed to hold good in the case of the complex copper base (red-violet) and its chloride (blue), as suggested by their respective magnetic moments of 1.7 and $1.92\mu_B$ (cf. Ray and Sen, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 473). Thus, the high solubility of these complexes in water with formation of their characteristic cations and their magnetic properties furnish definite evidences against their structure as inner-metallic compounds as suggested by Pfeiffer and Saure (*loc. cit.*).

In order to gain further insight into the behaviour of these compounds, the formation and stability of the diglycylethylenediamine complexes of the bivalent metals, zinc, cadmium and magnesium, besides copper and nickel, were studied, following the physico-chemical method of Bjerrum ("Metalamine Formation in Solution", P. Haase and Son, Copenhagen, 1941). The stability of the copper and nickel complexes were also studied from the decomposition of the respective complex bases, taking advantage of their availability in the free solid-state.

The reaction between diglycylethylenediamine dihydrochloride, $[\text{Digid H}_2] \text{Cl}_2$, and a bivalent metal ion M^{++} , may be assumed to take place in successive stages with the gradual addition of alkali, as represented below:

(where Digid = 1 molecule of diglycylethylenediamine).

The respective equilibrium constants K_f , K_{h_1} , and K_{h_2} , may be determined from the relations given below :

$$K_f = \frac{[M \text{ Diged}^{++}] \times [H^+]^2}{[M^{++}] \times [\text{Diged } H_2^{++}]} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

$$K_{h_1} = \frac{[(M \text{ Diged})(OH)]^+ \times [H^+]}{[M \text{ Diged}^{++}] \dots \dots (5)$$

$$\text{and } K_{h_2} = \frac{[(M \text{ Diged})(OH)_2] \times [H^+]}{[(M \text{ Diged})(OH)]^+} \dots \dots (6)$$

by measuring the p_H values of the reacting mixture during titration with a standard solution of carbonate-free alkali and knowing the acid dissociation constant values, k^*_2 and k^*_1 , of the ligand DigedH_2^{++} from the consideration of the following equations :

From these k^*_2 and k^*_1 , can be derived as

$$k^*_2 = \frac{[\text{Diged } H^+] \cdot [H^+]}{[\text{Diged } H_2^{++}]} \quad \dots \dots (9)$$

$$k^*_1 = \frac{[\text{Diged}] \cdot [H^+]}{[\text{Diged } H^+]} \quad \dots \dots (10)$$

The values of these constants, (k^*_2 and k^*_1), were determined by measuring the p_H values of the solution resulting from the progressive addition of alkali to the dihydrochloride of the base as described by De, Ghosh and Rây (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 493) for biguanide and substituted biguanides (cf. also Carlson, McReynolds and Verhoek, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1334).

While treating gradually a mixture of the metal ion and an excess of $(\text{Diged } H_2)^{++}$ in presence of some free acid with an alkali solution, if C denote the molar concentration of the total MCl_2 taken and C_0 , C_d , C_{h_1} and C_{h_2} , the respective molar concentrations of M^{++} , $[M \text{ Diged}]^{++}$, $[(M \text{ Diged})(OH)]^+$ and $[(M \text{ Diged})(OH)_2]$ present at any time, then

$$C = C_0 + C_d + C_{h_1} + C_{h_2} \quad \dots (11)$$

and if X denote the total diamine as dihydrochloride, then

$$X = B_0 + B_1 + B_2 + C_d + C_{h_1} + C_{h_2} \quad \dots (12)$$

where B_0 , B_1 and B_2 are the molar concentrations of Diged , $(\text{Diged } H)^+$ and $(\text{Diged } H_2)^{++}$ respectively. Further let P be the molar concentration of the added alkali (KOH) and A , the molar concentration of the initially present free acid in the reacting mixture at any time,

Now, as the solution is electrically neutral, the cationic and the anionic charges in it must be equal. Therefore,

$$i.e. 2C_0 + 2C_d + C_{h_1} + P + [H^+] + B_1 + 2B_2 = 2C + 2X + A + OH^- \quad \dots \quad (14)$$

Then, as the reactions (1), (2) and (3) take place with the release of acid (H^+ ion), there may arise three cases as shown below:

Case I. When the total acid disengaged is less than $2C$, the formation of $[(M \text{ Diged}) (\text{OH})]^+$ (vide eqn. (2)) and $[(M \text{ Diged}) (\text{OH})_2]$ [eqn. (3)] may be regarded as negligible. From (11), (12), (14), (9) and (10) assuming C_{h_1} and $C_{h_2} = 0$, we get

$$B_2 = \frac{[H^+]}{k^*_2 + 2[H^+]} \times (2X - P + A - [H^+] + [OH^-]) \quad \dots \quad (15)$$

$$C_d = 1/2 (P + [H^+] - A - [OH^-]) - \frac{[H^+] k^*_2 + 2k^*_1 k^*_2}{2[H^+] k^*_2 + 4[H^+]^2} (2X - P + A - [H^+] + [OH^-]) \quad (16)$$

$$C_0 = 1/2 (2C - P + A - [H^+] + [OH^-]) + \frac{[H^+] k^*_2 + k^*_1 k^*_2}{2[H^+] k^*_2 + 4[H^+]^2} = (2X - P + A - [H^+] + [OH^-]) \quad \dots (17)$$

From these,

$$K'_f = \frac{C_d \times [H^+]^2}{C_0 \times B_2} \quad \dots \quad (18)$$

The value of K'_f can also be obtained by plotting \bar{n}_d , the average ligandamine bound to metal atoms (given by C_d/C) against $(2p_H - p_{H_2})$. At $\bar{n}_d = 0.5$, the value of $[H^+]^2/B_2$ gives K'_f .

The instability or dissociation constant of the complex, $[M \text{ Diged}]^{++}$, is given by

$$\begin{aligned} K &= \frac{[M^{++}] \cdot [\text{Diged}]}{[M \text{ Diged}^{++}]} \\ &= \frac{[M^{++}] \cdot [\text{Diged H}_2^{++}]}{[M \text{ Diged}^{++}] \cdot [H^+]^2} \times \frac{[\text{Diged}] \cdot [H^+]^2}{[\text{Diged H}_2^{++}]} \\ &= k^*_1 k^*_2 / K'_f \quad \dots \quad (19) \end{aligned}$$

Case II. When the acid disengaged by complex formation is more than $2C$ but less than $3C$, the pure metal ion and the complex $[(M \text{ Diged}) (\text{OH})_2]$ may be considered as almost absent. Therefore from (11), (12) and (14) assuming C_0 and C_{h_2} equal to zero, we get

$$C_d = (3C - P - [H^+] + A - [OH^-]) + \frac{(X - C) (k^*_2 [H^+] + 2k^*_1 k^*_2)}{k^*_1 k^*_2 + k^*_2 [H^+] + 2[H^+]^2} \quad (20)$$

$$C_{h_1} = (P - 2C + [H^+] - A - [OH^-]) - \frac{(X-C) (k^*_{2}[H^+] + 2k^*_{1}k^*_{2})}{k^*_{1}k^*_{2} + k^*_{2}[H^+] + 2[H^+]^2} \quad (21)$$

From this K_{h_1} can be obtained from

$$K_{h_1} = \frac{C_{h_1} \times [H^+]}{C_d} \quad (22)$$

Case III. When the acid disengaged is greater than $3C$ but less than $4C$, the free metal ion, M^{++} , and the complex ion, $[MDiged]^{++}$, can be assumed to be almost absent and hence, $C_o = 0$ and $C_d = 0$, then the following relations may be obtained:

$$C_{h_1} = (4C - P - A - [H^+] + [OH^-]) + \frac{(X-C) (k^*_{2}[H^+] + 2k^*_{1}k^*_{2})}{k^*_{1}k^*_{2} + k^*_{2}[H^+] + 2[H^+]^2} \quad \dots (23)$$

$$\text{and } C_{h_2} = (P - 3C + [H^+] - A - [OH^-]) - \frac{(X-C) (k^*_{2}[H^+] + 2k^*_{1}k^*_{2})}{k^*_{1}k^*_{2} + k^*_{2}[H^+] + 2[H^+]^2} \quad \dots (24)$$

and hence the second hydrolytic constant can be derived from

$$K_{h_2} = \frac{C_{h_2} \times [H^+]}{C_{h_1}} \quad \dots (25)$$

Plotting \bar{n}_h , the average hydroxyl group bound to the metal complex, which can be represented as $(C_{h_1} + 2C_{h_2})/C$, against the corresponding p_H values, K_{h_1} and K_{h_2} can be evaluated when $\bar{n}_h = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. From the values of K_{h_1} and K_{h_2} , the corresponding dissociation constants of the complex base, $k^*_{b_1}$ and $k^*_{b_2}$, can be deduced from the usual equation,

$$k^*_{b_1} = \frac{K_w}{K_{h_1}}, \quad K_w \text{ being the ionic product of water.}$$

In a similar manner the stepwise decomposition of the complex base $[(M \text{ Diged}) (OH)_2]$ in the presence of increasing amounts of acid may be represented as follows:

and the respective equilibrium constants, K'_{h_2} , K'_{h_1} and K'_d are given by,

$$K'_{h_2} = \frac{[(M \text{ Diged}) (OH)]^+}{[(M \text{ Diged}) (OH)_2] \cdot [H^+]} \quad \dots (29)$$

$$K'_{h_1} = \frac{[M \text{ Digid}^{++}]}{[\{(M \text{ Digid}) (\text{OH})\}^+].[H^+]} \quad \dots \quad (30)$$

$$K'_d = \frac{[M^{++}].[Digid H_2^{++}]}{[M \text{ Digid}^{++}].[H^+]^2} \quad \dots \quad (31)$$

When a solution containing a known strength of the complex base $[(M \text{ Digid}) (\text{OH})_2]$ is titrated against a standard acid (HCl), the constants K'_{h_2} , K'_{h_1} and K'_d can be calculated from the measured p_H values of the mixture and the acid dissociation constants, k^*_1 and k^*_2 , of the ligand in the following way.

Let C be the concentration of the complex base originally present and let C_{h_2} , C_{h_1} , C_d and C_0 be the respective concentration of $[(M \text{ Digid})(\text{OH})_2]$, $[(M \text{ Digid})(\text{OH})]^+$, $[M \text{ Digid}]^{++}$ and M^{++} present in the reacting mixture at any time, then,

$$C = C_{h_2} + C_{h_1} + C_d + C_0 \quad \dots \quad (32)$$

The acid consumed by the reaction can be represented by $(A - [H^+])$, where A is the amount of the acid added;

$$A - [H^+] = C_{h_1} + 2C_d + 2B_0 + 3B_1 + 4B_2 \quad \dots \quad (33)$$

where B_0 , B_1 and B_2 are the concentrations of Digid, $[\text{Digid H}]^+$ and $[\text{Digid H}_2]^{++}$ respectively.

$$\text{Again, } C_0 = B_0 + B_1 + B_2 \quad \dots \quad (34)$$

There may arise three cases under these circumstances :

Case I. When the acid used up is less than C , only the reaction (26) takes place and so the ions, $[M \text{ Digid}]^{++}$ and M^{++} , and consequently Digid, $[\text{Digid H}]^+$ and $[\text{Digid H}_2]^{++}$ are absent. Assuming therefore C_d , C_0 , B_0 , B_1 and B_2 all to be negligibly small, we get from (32), (33) and (34)

$$C_{h_1} = A - [H^+] \quad \dots \quad (35)$$

$$C_{h_2} = C - A + [H^+] \quad \dots \quad (36)$$

Hence K'_{h_2} can be calculated from

$$K'_{h_2} = \frac{C_{h_1}}{C_{h_2} \times [H^+]} \quad \dots \quad (37)$$

Case II. When the acid consumed is more than C and less than $2C$, then the presence of $[(M \text{ Digid}) (\text{OH})_2]$, M^{++} , Digid, $[\text{Digid H}]^+$ and $[\text{Digid H}_2]^{++}$ may be assumed to be negligibly small. Then, from the set of equations (32-34), assuming C_{h_2} , C_0 , B_0 , B_1 and B_2 as zero, we get.

$$C_d = A - [H^+] - C \quad \dots \quad (38)$$

$$C_{h_1} = 2C - A + [H^+] \quad \dots \quad (39)$$

Hence, K'_{h_1} can be calculated from

$$K'_{h_1} = \frac{C_d}{C_{h_1} \times [H^+]} \quad \dots \quad (40)$$

The above two constants can also be obtained graphically by plotting \bar{n}_h , the average number of hydroxyl groups bound to the complex molecule, which is given by $(C_{h_1} + 2C_{h_2})/C$, against the p_H values and evaluating K'_{h_2} and K'_{h_1} , when $\bar{n}_h = 1.5$ and 0.5 respectively.

Case III. When the acid used up is more than $2C$ but less than $4C$, $[(M \text{ Diged}) (OH)_2]$ and $[(M \text{ Diged}) (OH)]^+$ may be taken as practically absent; then from the equations 32, 33 and 34, we obtain

$$B_2 = \frac{[H^+]}{k^*_{h_2} + 2[H^+]} (A - [H^+] - 2C) \quad \dots \quad (41)$$

$$C_0 = 1/2 (A - [H^+] - 2C) + \frac{[H^+] k^*_{h_2} + 2k^*_{h_1} k^*_{h_2}}{2 [H^+] k^*_{h_2} + 4[H^+]^2} (A - [H^+] - 2C) \quad (42)$$

$$C_d = 1/2 (4C - A + [H^+]) - \frac{[H^+] k^*_{h_2} + 2k^*_{h_1} k^*_{h_2}}{2 [H^+] k^*_{h_2} + 4 [H^+]^2} (A - [H^+] - 2C) \quad \dots \quad (43)$$

Hence K'_d can be calculated from

$$K'_d = \frac{C_0 \times B_2}{C_d \times [H^+]^2} \quad \dots \quad (44)$$

The value of K'_d can also be obtained graphically by plotting \bar{n}_d , the average ligand bound to the metal atom, which is C_d/C , against $2p_H - pB_2$; K'_d being calculated from the value of the latter corresponding to $\bar{n}_d = 0.5$.

Incidentally, it may be stated that the constants K'_d , K'_{h_1} and K'_{h_2} are respectively the reciprocals of the previous constants K'_f , K_{h_1} and K_{h_2} .

EXPERIMENTAL

Diglycylethylenediamine dihydrochloride was prepared according to the method of Cottrell and Gill (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 129) and recrystallised from aqueous alcohol, m.p. 246° (decomp.). The free base was also prepared from the dihydrochloride as described by them and the product was recrystallised from hot butanol.

1. *Copper diglycylethylenediamine Chloride.*—An excess of freshly precipitated copper hydroxide, washed free from all impurities, was digested on the water-bath with diglycylethylenediamine dihydrochloride, when a deep blue solution was obtained. This was filtered from the excess of copper hydroxide and poured into an equal volume of dioxane. On keeping overnight, the substance separated out in beautiful blue flakes. These are very soluble in water, but insoluble in organic solvents. $\chi_g = 4.992 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_M = 1.541 \times 10^{-3}$; $\mu_B = 1.92$.

[Found : Cu, 20.51 ; Cl, 23.1 ; N, 18.21. $[(C_6H_{14}O_2N_4)Cu]Cl_2$ requires Cu, 20.59; Cl, 22.9; N, 18.15 per cent].

2. *Copper diglycylethylenediamine hydroxide* was obtained by treating the complex chloride solution with an excess of moist silver oxide. A trace of silver also went into solution by complex formation. This was removed by adding a little copper chloride solution drop by drop till the filtrate from the silver chloride precipitate was free from both Ag and Cl ions. The filtrate, which had a permanganate like colour, was then evaporated to dryness in vacuum over concentrated sulphuric acid. The complex base was then obtained in red-violet flakes.

It can also be obtained by digesting freshly precipitated copper hydroxide with a solution of the free reagent base.

The substance is soluble in water yielding a deep permanganate-red solution, which reacts alkaline (p_H 9.0). On heating with ammonium salts, it evolves ammonia and the solution assumes a deep blue colour. A similar blue colour is also obtained by passing CO_2 through the red solution. The solid red compound gradually turns blue in atmospheric air. $\chi_g = 3.881 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m = 1.182 \times 10^{-3}$; $\mu_B = 1.72$. {Found : Cu, 19.97 ; N, 17.56. $[(C_6H_{14}O_2N_4)Cu](OH)_2 \cdot 2.5 H_2O$ requires Cu, 20.05 ; N, 17.6 per cent}. {Found (for the product dried at 110°) : Cu, 23.44 ; C, 26.8 ; H, 5.78. $[(C_6H_{14}O_2N_4)Cu](OH)_2$ requires Cu, 23.39 ; C, 26.5 ; H, 5.91 per cent}.

3. *Nickel diglycylethylenediamine chloride* was obtained like the corresponding copper salt by digesting an excess of nickel hydroxide with the hydrochloride of the reagent in aqueous solution. From the greenish blue filtrate, nickel diglycylethylenediamine chloride was precipitated as a sticky mass by the addition of alcohol. This was filtered and dried in vacuum. The substance forms a greenish blue hygroscopic powder, highly soluble in water. $\chi_B = 10.54 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m = 3.202 \times 10^{-3}$; $\mu_B = 2.8$. {Found : Ni, 19.01 ; Cl, 23.1. $[(C_6H_{14}O_2N_4)Ni]Cl_2$ requires Ni, 19.31 ; Cl, 23.3 per cent}.

4. *Nickel diglycylethylenediamine hydroxide* was obtained by treating an aqueous solution of the complex chloride with an excess of moist silver oxide. From the yellow solution the last trace of silver was removed by careful addition of dilute nickel chloride solution till the filtrate became free from both Ag and Cl ions. This was then evaporated in vacuum and the residue was digested with absolute alcohol. The product was finally dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid.

The substance forms a very hygroscopic yellow powder, which turns greenish blue in atmospheric air. Its aqueous solution is strongly alkaline (p_H 9.3). $\chi_g = -0.6437 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m = -0.1718 \times 10^{-3}$. {Found : Ni, 22.05 ; C, 26.5 ; H, 5.4 ; N, 21.11. $[(C_6H_{14}O_2N_4)Ni](OH)_2$ requires N, 21.9 ; C, 26.99 ; H, 5.28 ; N, 21.05 per cent}.

Magnetic susceptibilities of the substances were measured in a Gouy's balance.

Determination of the Instability Constants of the Metal Complexes

The following solutions were prepared :

(i) Copper chloride (0.05M in 0.01M free HCl), (ii) nickel chloride (0.05M in 0.01M free HCl), (iii) zinc chloride (0.05M in 0.0122M free HCl), (iv) cadmium chloride (0.05M in 0.044M free acid), (v) magnesium chloride (0.05M in 0.01M HCl). Merck's analytical reagents were used in all cases; (vi) ligand hydrochloride (0.05M) in molar KCl, (vii) caustic potash in M-KCl, freed from carbonate by treatment with baryta.

In all p_H measurements a Cambridge (bench type) p_H -potentiometer was used.

The method for the study of the formation constants of the metal complexes consisted in the addition of alkali to a solution of the metal chloride mixed with a little free hydrochloric acid and an excess of the reagent hydrochloride, and in measuring the p_H values of the solution after each addition.

In order to keep the ionic strength constant all the reactions were carried out in solutions containing KCl of 1 molar strength.

Fig. 1

Titration curves of $\text{DigidH}_2\text{Cl}_2$
with alkali.

\bar{n} —av. no. of H^+ bound to the ligand base.

Fig. 2

Titration curves of $\text{DigidH}_2\text{Cl}_2$
and M^{++} ions with alkali
(cf. Table II).

\bar{n}_d = av. no. of the ligand (Digid) moles bound to the metal ions.

[The curves from the top downwards represent respectively Mg, Cd, Zn, Ni and Cu ions.]

TABLE I

Acid dissociation constants of diglycylethylenediamine in salt solutions at 25°.

125 c.c. of 0.02M ligand dihydrochloride containing BaCl_2 (0.01M) and KCl (1M) titrated against 0.447M carbonate-free KOH solution (in M-KCl).

Alkali (moles/litre $\times 10^2$).	Strength of ligand (moles/litre $\times 10^2$).	p_H .	\bar{n} .	Alkali (moles/litre $\times 10^2$).	Strength of ligand (moles/litre $\times 10^2$).	p_H .	\bar{n} .
0.1781	1.992	6.520	1.91	2.0510	1.900	8.050	0.92
0.3555	1.976	6.950	1.82	2.2140	1.893	8.120	0.83
0.5312	1.968	7.150	1.73	2.3750	1.886	8.200	0.74
0.7053	1.960	7.310	1.64	2.5350	1.879	8.295	0.65
0.8781	1.953	7.410	1.55	2.6940	1.871	8.400	0.56
1.0480	1.945	7.525	1.46	2.8510	1.865	8.520	0.47
1.2180	1.937	7.620	1.37	3.0080	1.857	8.655	0.38
1.3900	1.929	7.710	1.28	3.1630	1.852	8.820	0.29
1.5560	1.923	7.800	1.19	3.3180	1.845	9.050	0.20
1.7230	1.915	7.890	1.10	3.4700	1.838	9.450	0.11
1.8890	1.907	7.970	1.01	3.6230	1.830	10.360	0.02

$pK_2^* = 7.63$

$pK_1^* = 8.35$

$pK^*(av) = 7.99$

From the curve obtained by plotting \bar{n} against p_H , the approximate values of K_1^* and K_2^* were obtained from the p_H values at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and $\bar{n} = 1.5$ respectively. By substituting these approximate values to the general equation, the more precise values for these were calculated (cf. Carlson, McReynolds and Verhoek, loc. cit.).

TABLE II

Formation and hydrolysis of copper diglycylethylenediamine complex.

25 c.c. of 0.05M of copper chloride in 0.01M-HCl and 50 c.c. of the reagent hydrochloride (0.05M) made up with KCl solution to 125 c.c. to make it 1 M in KCl.

Strength (in moles/litre $\times 10^3$) of

Alkali.	Metal.	Ligand.	Free acid.	p_H .	$2p_H - p_{OH}$.	\bar{n}_d .	\bar{n}
0.1781	0.9961	1.992	0.1992	3.130	4.55	0.027	..
0.5301	0.9831	1.976	0.1976	3.940	6.14	0.174	..
0.8764	0.9804	1.961	0.1961	4.470	7.15	0.348	..
1.0470	0.9766	1.953	0.1953	4.670	7.53	0.436	..
1.2170	0.9727	1.945	0.1945	4.850	7.86	0.525	..
1.5530	0.9651	1.930	0.1930	5.180	8.45	0.699	..
1.8850	0.9585	1.916	0.1916	5.565	9.10	0.879	..
2.2100	0.9506	1.901	0.1901	6.150	0.092
2.5300	0.9434	1.887	0.1887	6.500	0.399
2.8880	0.9397	1.879	0.1879	6.640	0.576
2.8450	0.9363	1.873	0.1873	6.780	0.708
3.1570	0.9294	1.859	0.1859	7.140	0.928
3.4630	0.9226	1.845	0.1845	7.510	1.030
3.7660	0.9158	1.832	0.1832	7.800	1.102
4.0630	0.9090	1.818	0.1818	8.040	1.216
4.3560	0.9024	1.805	0.1805	8.230	1.374
4.6460	0.8960	1.792	0.1792	8.450	1.526
4.9320	0.8898	1.779	0.1779	8.700	1.696
5.2130	0.8835	1.767	0.1767	9.140	1.914

TABLE III

Acid decomposition of copper diglycylethylenediamine hydroxide.

0.01162M complex base in 1M-KCl titrated against 0.1142 M-HCl (in M-KCl).

Acid (moles/litre $\times 10^3$).	Complex (moles/litre $\times 10^3$).	p_H .	\bar{n}_d .	\bar{n} .	$2p_H - p_H$
0.0906	1.1510	8.85	1.922
0.2676	1.1320	8.65	1.762
0.4392	1.1150	8.50	1.605
0.5230	1.1070	8.47	1.528
0.6054	1.0980	8.44	1.448
1.0000	1.0590	7.77	1.055
1.1010	1.0510	7.56	0.953
1.2950	1.0280	7.02	0.740
1.5070	1.0070	6.80	0.503
1.7740	0.9797	6.29	0.189
2.1500	0.9417	6.00	..	0.857	9.13
2.3940	0.9177	5.66	..	0.699	8.76
2.5540	0.9007	5.37	..	0.581	8.31
2.6630	0.8896	5.12	..	0.502	7.88
2.8200	0.8736	4.90	..	0.385	7.53
3.0720	0.8480	3.87	..	0.181	5.68

TABLE IV

Initial concentrations before titration of the solutions employed.

(a) Formation experiments.

Initial conc. (moles/litre $\times 10^3$) of

	Initial volume.	Metal.	Free acid.	Ligand.	Initial p_H .	KCl.
Copper	125 c.c.	1	0.1	2	2.77	1 M
Nickel	125	1	0.1	2	2.77	"
Zinc	125	1	0.2440	2	2.7	"
Cadmium	125	1	0.4444	2	2.43	"
Magnesium	125	1	0.1	2	2.77	"

(b) Decomposition experiments.

	Volume:	Complex base (moles/litre $\times 10^2$)	p_H .	KCl.
Copper	125 c.c.	1.168	9.00	1 M
Nickel	125	1.104	9.30	1

TABLE V-

Values of the various constants.

	Copper.	Nickel.	Zinc.	Cadmium.	Magnesium.
pK'_{f_1}	7.85 (2)	10.56 (2)	11.87 (2)	12.65 (2)	15.44* (2)
$\log K'$	7.87 (4)	10.56 (4)
pK	8.13	5.42	4.31	3.33	0.54*
pK_{h_2}	8.43 (3)	8.04 (3)
pK_{h_1}	6.58 (3)	7.04 (3)
$\log K'_{h_1}$	6.59 (5)	7.03 (5)
$\log K_{h_2}$	8.40 (5)	8.03 (5)
$pK^*_{b_1}$	7.38	6.92
$pK^*_{b_2}$	5.53	5.02

(2), (3) (4) and (5) indicate the Fig. No. of the curves from which the values were derived.

Fig. 3

Titration curves showing hydrolysis of the complex (cf. Table II).

\bar{n}_h = av. no. of OH bound to the complex radical; upper—Ni, lower—Cu.

Fig. 4

Titration curves of the complex base with acid till neutralisation (cf. Table III).

\bar{n}_h = av. no. of OH bound to the complex radical; upper—Ni, lower—Cu.

In the case of copper and nickel complexes determination of the instability constants was also made from a study of their decomposition by means of acids. For this purpose a solution of the copper or the nickel base in molar KCl was titrated against standard HCl (in M-KCl) and the p_H value of the solution after each addition was measured.

Acid dissociation constants of diglycylethylenediamine were determined by titrating with standard alkali a solution of the hydrochloride of the base in 1M-KCl containing 0.01M-BaCl₂ and measuring the p_H values after each addition.

The results of measurements are given in Tables I to V and represented graphically in Figs. 1-5.

Fig. 5

Titration curves showing the decomposition of the complex
(cf. Table III).

\bar{n}_d = av. no. of the ligand bound to the metal ion.
 $p_{Ba^{2+}}$ = - log. of the ligand dihydrochloride conc.
{upper—Ni; lower—Cu}

DISCUSSION

The acid dissociation constants k_1^* and k_2^* of diglycylethylenediamine were found to have the values 4.467×10^{-9} and 2.344×10^{-8} respectively. The average value, $k_{av}^* = \sqrt{k_1^* k_2^*}$, is therefore equal to 1.023×10^{-8} . This shows, as might have been expected, that it is a weaker base than ethylenediamine for which the corresponding values are 1.2×10^{-10} , 6.4×10^{-8} and 2.8×10^{-9} (Carlson, *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). It is, however, somewhat stronger than glycine for which these values are 2.82×10^{-10} , 5.75×10^{-8} and 1.27×10^{-6} respectively (Das Sarma, *this Journal* 1952, 29, 217).

The stability of the complexes determined follow the same general order, viz., Cu > Ni > Zn > Cd > Mg, as is the case with complexes of the above metals with many other ligands. The pK values for complexes of the above metals with this ligand, as well as with ethylenediamine and ammonia, are given below for comparison.

TABLE VI

	p_K values for complexes of				
	Cu.	Ni.	Zn.	Cd.	Mg.
Ammonia	12.6	7.8	8.1	6.9	—
Ethylenediamine	19.6	18.08	12.09	12.09	—
Diglycylethylenediamine	8.13	5.42	4.31	3.33	0.54

It shows that the ligand diglycylethylenediamine is a much weaker co-ordinating or complexing agent than even ammonia. This seems apparently to support Calvin and Wilson's suggestion (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003) about the relation between the basic character of the ligand and its complex forming capacity.

The character of the ligand as a weaker base and as a weaker co-ordinating agent is also evident from the fact that of the four co-ordinating or electron-donating nitrogen atoms, two are derived from the amido groups.

The hydrolytic constants K_{h_1} and K_{h_2} could be determined only for copper and nickel complexes. The cadmium and zinc compounds are more or less completely decomposed into the corresponding insoluble hydroxides above p_H 8. From these, the dissociation constants $k^*_{b_1}$ and $k^*_{b_2}$ of the complex bases were deduced.

The hydrolysis constants of the complex copper and nickel salts have been calculated on the assumption that the corresponding complex bases are very weak, and hence, occur almost in the undissociated state in aqueous solution. This may not be strictly correct. Nevertheless, that the ionic dissociation of the complex bases is strongly depressed in the presence of an excess of alkali is revealed by the colour change of the copper base with the increase of alkali added. The violet-red solution of the complex copper base assumes a deep pink tint like that of permanganate with an excess of alkali. The values of hydrolytic constants show that the copper complex ($K_{h_1}=2.63 \times 10^{-7}$ and $K_{h_2}=3.72 \times 10^{-9}$) is somewhat more hydrolysed than the corresponding nickel compound ($K_{h_1}=0.912 \times 10^{-7}$ and $K_{h_2}=1.15 \times 10^{-9}$). The values of the corresponding dissociation constants $k^*_{b_1}$ and $k^*_{b_2}$ are 4.17×10^{-8} and 3.02×10^{-6} for Cu, and 12.02×10^{-8} and 9.55×10^{-6} for Ni. This shows that as a base the nickel complex is somewhat stronger than the corresponding copper base.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA 9.

Received December 10, 1952.